

Impacts of Precipitation on Outbreak of Cryptosporidiosis Risk in Tennessee, 2012- 2021

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Abstract

The surge in precipitation is forecast to lead to a rise in cryptosporidiosis, a waterborne acute gastrointestinal infection. This study investigates the association between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis in Tennessee from 2012 to 2021 using time series analysis and Distributed Lag Nonlinear Models (DLNM). The findings reveal significant seasonal trends in cryptosporidiosis cases, with periodic spikes right after rains. While simple Poisson regression found no immediate association, DLNM revealed delayed and nonlinear effects. Moderate rainfall (1–3 inches) increased cryptosporidiosis risk within 2 weeks, whereas heavy rainfall (≥ 5 inches) showed a protective effect up to 4 weeks. A renewed increase in risk emerged at 6–10-week lags, particularly following light rainfall. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating lagged climate effects into disease surveillance and support targeted public health interventions after rainfall events to help mitigate cryptosporidiosis outbreaks.

Key Words: Distributed Lag Models, Time Series, Precipitation, Cryptosporidiosis, Predictive Analysis, R

1. Introduction

Precipitation events are becoming more intense and frequent in United States. According to US environmental protection agency [1], extreme single-day precipitation events have risen by about half a percent per decade since 1910. Moreover, reports from NOAA [2] and US global change research program [3] have highlighted the potential impacts of heavy rainfall that can significantly increase flood risk, soil erosion, and damage crops. These extreme precipitation events pose risks to public health, in particular affect the gastrointestinal and respiratory systems, along with various other health consequences. Literature has identified extreme weather events such as heavy rainfall, flooding, elevated temperatures, and prolonged drought as key factors contributing to the contamination of water sources with pathogens. These conditions create an environment that facilitates outbreaks of waterborne diseases, including gastroenteritis, cryptosporidiosis, giardiasis, and cholera [4], [5]. Several studies [6]–[9] have shown an association between cryptosporidiosis and giardiasis and precipitation. In this research, we have examined the exposure-outcome relationship between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis in Tennessee, from 2012 – 2021.

Cryptosporidiosis caused by the protozoan parasite cryptosporidium, is of great concern in Tennessee. This parasite is found in variety of environments, including water, food, soil, and surfaces that have been contaminated with fecal matter. Research findings in paper [10], have shown significant associations between cryptosporidiosis and surface water impairment, geology, animal density and land use type such as developed and pasture land in East Tennessee. Study done by [8] and [11], revealed a strong association between exposure to treated recreational water and livestock and the occurrence of cryptosporidiosis. According to 2019 Cryptosporidiosis Summary Report

[12], cryptosporidiosis is the leading cause of waterborne disease outbreaks in US. Moreover, according to 2019 report, the incidence of cryptosporidiosis has increased by 47.2% during the last decade and for Tennessee the incidence rate was 3.6 per 100,000 population.

The 2021 Annual Surveillance Report [13], indicated that there were 5 recreational associated waterborne outbreaks in US. For the recreational waterborne outbreaks, it was found that all the 22 confirmed cases reported in Tennessee were due to *cryptosporidium parvum*/ *cryptosporidium hominis*. Also, projections from National Climate Assessment (NCA 5) [14] report have stated that heavy precipitation are increasing in US and will continue to increase in the future. Thus, there is a need for integrated climate resilient water management strategies and robust health surveillance systems to mitigate the impact of heavy precipitation on infectious disease transmission.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data collection process. Section 3 presents the exploratory data analysis, focusing on precipitation patterns and the time series of cryptosporidiosis cases. In Section 4, we apply time series decomposition, followed by the implementation of both linear and nonlinear distributed lag Poisson models in Section 5. Section 6 provides a detailed discussion on the distributed lag model results. Finally, Section 7 concludes and offers recommendations for future work. All analyses were conducted using R software [15].

2. Data Collection

This research focused on the confirmed cryptosporidiosis cases reported and the amount of precipitation that happened in Tennessee from 2012-2021. Tennessee is in southeastern United States and is exposed to warm and humid air from Gulf of Mexico and hot/cold air masses from North America interior [16].

2.1 Cryptosporidiosis cases

Cryptosporidiosis case data were extracted for the period January 1, 2012, to December 31, 2021, from the National Notifiable Diseases Surveillance System (NNDSS) [17], a system jointly managed by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the Council of State and Territorial Epidemiologists (CSTE). NNDSS publishes weekly reports of nationally notifiable infectious diseases on its public-facing website. These data are derived from passive surveillance and reflect reports submitted to local and state health departments [18].

The NNDSS reports provide cumulative weekly case counts for both the current and previous year. To get the latest weekly counts for the current year, we looked at the counts of cryptosporidiosis cases for the current year, in the next year weekly data. To calculate weekly incident cryptosporidiosis cases, we derived the difference between the cumulative count for the current week and that of the previous week. This method allowed for an accurate estimation of newly reported cases each week. All weekly data were manually extracted and compiled in Microsoft Excel for subsequent statistical analysis.

Because the NNDSS resets its weekly reporting cycle annually, starting from week 1 each year (52 weekly totals), particular care was taken during year transitions to ensure weekly case counts were assigned correctly. This vigilance was essential to maintain consistency and accuracy across the dataset.

2.2 Precipitation Data

Daily precipitation (inches/day) data was extracted from The Climate Toolbox webpage [19], created by University of California, Merced. As the original data were provided in a daily format, a manual data collection process was employed using Excel to compile and sum daily values into weekly totals. This aggregation produced weekly precipitation values for the state of Tennessee for the period spanning 2012 to 2021, enabling analysis of temporal patterns and their potential association with cryptosporidiosis incidence.

3. Exploratory Data Analysis

We began with an exploratory analysis to gain an initial understanding of the data. Summary statistics and scatterplots (shown under Time Series Analysis and Decomposition) were generated to examine the distribution and variability of cryptosporidiosis cases and weekly precipitation. Additionally, boxplots were constructed to visually assess the relationship between precipitation levels and reported case counts, providing preliminary insight into potential associations and patterns.

3.1 Summary Statistics for Cryptosporidiosis cases and Precipitation

Between 2012 and 2021, a total of 1,737 confirmed cryptosporidiosis cases were reported to the NNDSS in Tennessee. Weekly case counts ranged from 0 to 22, with a mean of 3.34 cases. During the same period, weekly precipitation ranged from 0 to 7.37 inches, with an average of 1.15 inches. Extreme precipitation events were most frequent from December through April, with the highest value observed in February.

3.2 Boxplot

To better understand the temporal relationship between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis incidence, we examined boxplots of both variables (Figure 1a and 1b). Figure 1a shows that precipitation levels tend to be higher between December and April, corresponding to Tennessee's typical rainy season, which spans late winter through spring. In contrast, cryptosporidiosis cases (Figure 1b) peak between July and late October, with the highest count of 22 occurring in August. Also, it was noted that there were fewer cases reported during the high-precipitation months. This temporal mismatch suggests a potential delayed effect of rainfall on disease incidence. Additionally, outliers are present in both variables: in precipitation, these likely represent episodes of extreme rainfall, while in case counts, they may indicate localized outbreaks or reporting anomalies. These observations warrant further investigation of delayed effects, which are explored in subsequent analyses.

Figure 1: Boxplot for (a) Precipitation (inches/week) and (b) Cryptosporidiosis cases (weekly for Tennessee from 2012 – 2021, grouped by Month

4. Time Series Analysis and Decomposition

4.1 Cryptosporidiosis

Figure 2 displays all confirmed cryptosporidiosis cases reported to the NNDSS from 2012 to 2021. Notably, no cases were reported in 2013, which is likely due to a reporting gap or human error, as the CDC has documented cases consistently since 1995, according to the 2019 Cryptosporidiosis Summary Report [11]. The highest annual case count occurred in 2015. The time series plot (Figure 2) of weekly cases reveals substantial temporal variability, with frequent spikes likely reflecting seasonal outbreaks or localized increases in transmission. A smoothed trend line indicates a gradual rise in cases from 2012 through 2018, followed by a plateau in subsequent years. This trend suggests potential shifts in cryptosporidiosis dynamics over time, which may be influenced by changes in environmental conditions, public health reporting practices, intervention strategies, or population-level behavioral patterns.

Figure 2: Time Series plot for Cryptosporidiosis cases (weekly), with a smooth trend line

Time series decomposition (Figure3) provides further insights by disaggregating the cryptosporidiosis data into trend, seasonal, and residual components. The trend component reveals a marked increase in reported cases from 2013 to 2016, followed by a stabilization in subsequent years. The seasonal component exhibits clear annual periodicity, indicating a consistent temporal pattern likely influenced by climatic conditions or seasonal human behaviors. The residual (random) component captures short-term fluctuations not explained by trend or seasonality, potentially attributable to isolated outbreaks, reporting delays, or anomalies in data collection. Together, these components confirm that cryptosporidiosis incidence is shaped by long-term trends, recurrent seasonal effects, and episodic irregularities.

Figure 3: Time Series Decomposition for Cryptosporidiosis cases (weekly)

4.2 Precipitation Patterns

Figure 4 presents the weekly precipitation trends in Tennessee from 2012 to 2021, revealing high-frequency variability marked by numerous short-term peaks and troughs. The most extreme rainfall event, approximately 7.1 inches, occurred in 2019. Notable spikes in precipitation were observed around 2018 and 2020, corresponding to periods of heightened weather activity. Despite these fluctuations, the overall smoothed trend line remains relatively stable, indicating no substantial long-term increase or decrease in average weekly precipitation throughout the study period.

Figure 4: Time Series plot for Precipitation(inches/weekly), with a smooth trend line

Figure 5 presents the decomposition of the weekly precipitation time series, highlighting key structural patterns. The trend component indicates a modest increase in average precipitation from 2012 followed by a gradual decline till mid 2016. From 2017 onwards, rains increased till earlier part of 2020, followed by a slight decline toward the end of the study period. While the seasonal component reveals recurring patterns, these seasonal fluctuations are less pronounced than those observed in cryptosporidiosis cases, suggesting weaker seasonal influence on precipitation. The irregular component captures high-frequency variation and sharp deviations, likely attributable to isolated extreme weather events, such as heavy storms or flash flooding.

Figure 5: Time Series Decomposition for Precipitation(inches/weekly)

These findings confirm that while precipitation exhibits short-term variability and episodic extremes, it remains relatively stable in the long term. The presence of both seasonal and random effects supports its role as a dynamic environmental factor that may influence cryptosporidiosis incidence through lagged or nonlinear pathways.

4.3 ACF and PACF for Cryptosporidiosis cases and Precipitation

4.3.2 Cryptosporidiosis cases

The ACF plot shows a gradual decay in autocorrelation across lags, suggesting that weekly cryptosporidiosis cases are influenced by past case numbers over multiple weeks, with stronger correlations at shorter lags. The PACF plot reveals significant partial autocorrelations at the first lag, indicating that the most influential predictor for weekly cases is the immediately preceding week, while the impact of longer lags is minimal.

4.3.2 Precipitation

The ACF plot indicates weak autocorrelations across lags, suggesting limited direct influence of past precipitation values on future ones. Most autocorrelation values lie within the confidence intervals, reflecting minimal significant correlation beyond lag 0. The PACF plot shows minor significant spikes at the initial lags, suggesting a weak relationship between precipitation values and their immediate past, but no strong partial autocorrelation at higher lags. These findings imply that precipitation data may have limited temporal dependencies, with little influence from past values.

Figure 6: ACF and PACF for Cryptosporidiosis cases and Precipitation

5. Methods and Results

We used Poisson Regression Models to study the relationship between cryptosporidiosis and precipitation in Tennessee from 2012- 2021. We started with simple Poisson regression linear model and as the findings were not significant, we applied Poisson regression model with a distributed lag non-linear model [20], [21].

5.1 Poisson Regression Linear Models

A standard Poisson regression model was employed to examine the immediate association between weekly precipitation and reported cases of cryptosporidiosis in Tennessee over the period 2012-2021. Weekly cryptosporidiosis case counts were modeled as the dependent variable, while weekly total precipitation (in inches) was included as the sole independent variable. The model assumes a Poisson distribution with a log-link function, defined as:

$$\log [E(Y_t)] = b_0 + b_1 x_t$$

where Y_t corresponds to the historical weekly cryptosporidiosis cases and x_t represents precipitation at time t .

The regression output indicated that the intercept was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), with an estimated log count of 1.193, representing the expected log-number of cryptosporidiosis cases when precipitation is zero. However, the coefficient for precipitation was not statistically significant (Estimate = 0.00988, Standard Error = 0.0253, $z = 0.391$, $p = 0.696$). This result suggests that there is no significant linear relationship between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis incidence when modeled as an immediate, same-week effect.

Model diagnostics further support this conclusion. The residual deviance (1601.9 on 517 degrees of freedom) was nearly identical to the null deviance (1602.0), indicating that the model explained minimal variability in cryptosporidiosis outcomes. Additionally, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) value of 2888.2 reflects a relatively poor model fit.

In summary, these findings suggest that precipitation alone, when modeled as an immediate linear predictor, does not significantly influence weekly cryptosporidiosis case counts. These findings underscore the limitations of the standard Poisson regression approach in this context and highlight the need for more advanced modeling techniques, such as DLNM, which are better suited according to literature, to capturing delayed and nonlinear effects of environmental exposures on health outcomes.

5.2 Poisson Regression Non - Linear Models

A Poisson regression model with a DLNM framework was applied to examine the association between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis cases, incorporating lagged effects and adjusting for seasonality using natural cubic splines. This approach allows for more accurate assessment of delayed and nonlinear relationships in environmental health data.

The basic model representation [21] that describes the time series outcome Y_t is given by

$$\log [E(Y_t)] = \alpha + f(x_t; \theta) + s(t; \beta)$$

where Y_t corresponds to the historical weekly cryptosporidiosis cases and assumed to follow a Poisson distribution with overdispersion, the function $f(x_t; \theta)$ specifies the association with precipitation (environmental exposure) denoted by x at time t and $s(t; \beta)$ represents the baseline trend that captures the seasonal and long-term trends. The exposure-response association modeled by the function f , is a distributed lag non-linear model through a bi-dimensional cross-basis term, using flexible natural cubic spline functions to model both exposure-response and lagged-response dimensions [21].

In our research, we focused on time lags that demonstrated a significant association between weekly cryptosporidiosis cases and precipitation. Our findings revealed that lags of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 weeks showed notable correlations.

5.2.1 DLNM for Lag = 2 weeks

Figure 7 (left side) presents the contour plot derived from a DLNM, which assesses the short-term effects of weekly precipitation on the relative risk (RR) of cryptosporidiosis in Tennessee, using a maximum lag of 2 weeks. The x-axis represents weekly precipitation amounts (in inches), while the y-axis reflects the lag time in weeks. The contour shading visualizes RR, where red zones represent increased risk ($RR > 1.0$), and blue zones represent decreased risk ($RR < 1.0$).

The analysis indicates that lower precipitation levels (approximately 1–3 inches) are associated with a moderate increase in cryptosporidiosis risk, particularly at a 1-week lag. This suggests a short-term exposure-response relationship that may result from contaminated surface runoff, microbial mobilization, or ingestion of untreated water following light-to-moderate rainfall. The peak relative risk appears around 1 inch of precipitation at a lag of 1–2 weeks, highlighting a potential window of vulnerability for public health. Moreover, Figure 7 (right side), confirms the finding given by the contour plot. The lag effects given by Figure 7 (right side) reflects that there is an association between cases and precipitation, compared with no precipitation. RR value and their 95% confidence intervals (CI) for lag 1 and 2 weeks are 0.88 (0.67, 1.16), 0.82 (0.63, 1.07) respectively.

Conversely, heavy rainfall events (≥ 5 inches) are associated with a notable reduction in cases across all short-term lags (0–2 weeks). This inverse association may be attributed to dilution effects, where pathogen concentrations are lowered in water systems, or to reduced exposure behavior, such as less outdoor water contact during and immediately after severe weather.

Figure 7: DLNM Analysis of Precipitation on Cryptosporidiosis (Lag = 2 weeks)

In summary, this DLNM analysis suggests that moderate rainfall increases cryptosporidiosis risk within a short timeframe, while heavier rainfall may have a protective effect in the short term. These results underscore the importance of lag-aware disease surveillance and support the development of early public health warning systems triggered by moderate precipitation levels.

5.2.2 DLNM for Lag = 4 weeks

Contour plot (Figure 8 (left side)) generated from the DLNM illustrates the relationship between weekly precipitation and RR of cryptosporidiosis cases in Tennessee over a maximum lag of 4 weeks. The results indicate that higher precipitation levels (≥ 3 inches) are consistently associated with reduced cases risk across all lag periods up to 4 weeks. This protective pattern, visualized by the prominent blue region, may reflect dilution effects, where heavy rainfall decreases the

concentration of fecal pathogens in environmental water sources. It may also suggest behavioral avoidance of contaminated environments during and after extreme weather.

In contrast, slightly elevated cases risk is observed at low precipitation levels (0–2 inches) during the week following rainfall (lag 1-4). This modest increase may be attributed to surface runoff, initial microbial contamination, or short-term exposure to untreated water soon after light rainfall events. The above observations are also confirmed by Figure 8 (right side). The detailed specific estimates shows that RR (0.942) is the highest for 1 inch precipitation level with a 95% confidence interval of (0.67, 1.32). Furthermore, the overall estimated RR and 95% confidence intervals at lags 1 – 4 weeks, when compared to zero precipitation are 0.96 (0.87, 1.06), 1.01 (0.89, 1.15), 1.03 (0.94, 1.41), 1.04 (0.88, 1.22) respectively.

Over time, the relative risk trends downward across all precipitation levels, reinforcing the likelihood of short-term exposure windows and the mitigating effects of environmental dilution or delayed response interventions.

Figure 8: DLNM Analysis of Precipitation on Cryptosporidiosis (Lag = 4 weeks)

Overall, the DLNM results suggest that light-to-moderate rainfall may pose a short-term risk for cryptosporidiosis, while heavier precipitation appears to reduce risk, especially beyond the first week. These findings support timely public health advisories and targeted water quality monitoring following rainfall events, particularly those under 3 inches.

5.2.3 DLNM for Lag = 6 weeks

The contour plot given by Figure 9 (left side), demonstrates a notable reduction in cases risk associated with higher precipitation levels (≥ 4 inches) across lags 1 to 4 weeks. This protective effect may result from dilution of contaminants, disruption of exposure pathways, or reduced human contact with contaminated sources following heavy rainfall. In contrast, the model reveals a distinct area of elevated risk at lag 5 to 6 weeks, for all precipitation levels (1-7 inches). This delayed peak suggests a secondary effect possibly due to persistent environmental contamination, bacterial regrowth, or delayed infrastructure failures. Figure 9 (right side) also reflects the RR increase in cases for lags 4 – 6 weeks. The detailed estimates show that RR is highest for 7-inch precipitation at lag 6 with a RR value of 1.36 and 95% CI of (0.78, 2.38).

Figure 9: DLNM Analysis of Precipitation on Cryptosporidiosis (Lag = 6 weeks)

These findings highlight the nonlinear and lagged nature of precipitation’s impact on cryptosporidiosis risk. Importantly, the results emphasize the need for timely and prolonged public health surveillance following rainfall events, not only in the immediate aftermath but also several weeks later, especially after moderate precipitation levels.

5.2.4 DLNM for Lag = 8 weeks

Figure 10 presents result from a DLNM with a maximum lag of 8 weeks. The contour plot (left) and the lag-response curve (right) reveal a delayed increase in cryptosporidiosis risk between 6 - 8 weeks following precipitation events ranging from 0 to 7 inches. This pattern suggests the presence of secondary exposure pathways or environmental persistence of pathogens. During the early lag period (lags 1–3 weeks), risk remains low across all precipitation levels, reinforcing the delayed nature of the association.

Notably, the lag-response plot (Figure 10, right) shows a progressive increase in RR from lag 4 to lag 8 weeks when compared to zero precipitation. The highest estimated RR is observed at lag 8 for 3 inches of rainfall, with a value of 1.24 and a 95% confidence interval of (1.15, 1.43). These findings underscore the importance of accounting for longer lag periods when assessing environmental drivers of cryptosporidiosis and may inform public health surveillance strategies and timing of interventions.

Figure 10: DLNM Analysis of Precipitation on Cryptosporidiosis (Lag = 8 weeks)

Looking at the trend of DLNM for different lag weeks (2-8), we decided to go further and look for association at 10 – week lags.

5.2.5 DLNM for Lag = 10 weeks

Figure 11 presents a DLNM contour plot (left) examining the effects of precipitation on cryptosporidiosis risk with a maximum lag of 10 weeks. The results reveal a pronounced delayed increase in risk between 5 and 8 weeks following low precipitation levels (0–2 inches), as indicated by the deep red zone. This suggests potential secondary exposure pathways, such as bacterial regrowth in water systems, infrastructure-related contamination, or prolonged environmental persistence of pathogens. In contrast, higher precipitation levels (≥ 4 inches) show less risk between 6 to 8 weeks.

The lag-response plot (Figure 11, right) corroborates these findings, showing elevated RR from lags 3 to 10 weeks. The highest RR is observed at lag 6 for 1 inch of precipitation, with an RR of 1.15 and a 95% confidence interval of (1.06, 1.26). These findings emphasize the importance of accounting for long-term lag effects in waterborne disease modeling and suggest the need for ongoing post-event monitoring following even modest rainfall.

Figure 11: DLNM Analysis of Precipitation on Cryptosporidiosis (Lag = 10 weeks)

6. Discussion

The progression from simple Poisson regression to Distributed Lag Nonlinear Models revealed critical insights into the complex temporal dynamics between precipitation and cryptosporidiosis incidence in Tennessee from 2012 to 2021. The linear Poisson regression model, which only accounted for same-week effects, did not find a statistically significant association between weekly precipitation and reported cases.

However, the application of DLNM, which captures both delayed and nonlinear relationships, uncovered important patterns that were otherwise undetectable. In the short term (lags 0–2 weeks), moderate precipitation (1–3 inches) was associated with increased cryptosporidiosis risk, suggesting rapid exposure routes through runoff or contaminated water, whereas heavier rainfall (≥ 5 inches) appeared to reduce risk, likely due to dilution effects or behavioral changes.

During intermediate lags (up to 4 weeks), this protective trend with higher precipitation persisted, while light rainfall continued to present modest risks. Notably, a shift occurred at lag 6, where moderate precipitation became linked to delayed increases in disease risk, implying possible environmental persistence of pathogens or infrastructure vulnerabilities.

At longer lags, particularly at 8 and 10 weeks, the analyses showed delayed spikes in relative risk, with lag 8 showing elevated risk across all rainfall levels, especially at 3 inches, and lag 10 highlighting heightened risk following low precipitation (0–2 inches) after 5–8 weeks. These delayed effects may reflect secondary transmission pathways, bacterial regrowth, or infrastructure-induced contamination.

Collectively, the findings emphasize the importance of moving beyond simple models when examining environmental health outcomes and demonstrate the value of DLNM in identifying temporally distributed risks. They further highlight the need for sustained public health surveillance and the development of early warning systems, particularly following moderate rainfall, to effectively mitigate cryptosporidiosis risk.

7. Conclusion, Future Research, and Recommendations

Our findings indicate clear seasonal patterns in cryptosporidiosis cases, with noticeable spikes occurring shortly after rainfall events. Although basic Poisson regression model did not show an immediate relationship, the distributed lag nonlinear model uncovered delayed and nonlinear effects. Cryptosporidiosis risk increased within 2 weeks after moderate rainfall (1-3 inches) and heavy rainfall (≥ 5 inches) showed a protective effect up to 4 weeks. At 6–10-week lags, there was a renewed increase in risk following a light rainfall. In future, we plan to explore the inclusion of additional environmental and microbiological variables, such as temperature, humidity, and pathogen concentrations, to better understand the multifactorial drivers of cryptosporidiosis risk. Expanding the application of distributed lag non-linear models to other geographic regions could help assess the generalizability of findings and reveal spatial patterns in precipitation-related health outcomes. Moreover, investigating the role of infrastructure and socioeconomic factors may provide insights into population vulnerability and exposure pathways. From a public health perspective, implementing real-time water quality monitoring and early warning systems following rainfall events could enhance preparedness and response. Public education campaigns focused on safe water practices, especially after precipitation, can reduce exposure risks. Additionally, improvements to sewer infrastructure and routine testing of private wells are critical steps to protect communities from waterborne diseases.

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